

We thought we knew what we were talking about: The (de)conceptualisation of LIS.

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Abstract: This conceptual short paper examines the process of theoretical development by presenting the work that an informal network of researchers is doing to conceptualise transition through an information lens. The paper's focus on the collaborative process extends the traditional individual researcher narratives of conceptual work including tacit and often taken for granted processes of theoretical development.

Keywords: Conceptual development, Research collaboration

According to Sonnenwald (2016), the past decade has seen a growing interest in discussing theory use in library and information science (LIS), whereas the journey – the process of theory development - is often left behind. Questions that are often overlooked include how theory development looks from the inside and what factors influence, trigger, or drive conceptual work. At the same time, theory development that has taken place in LIS has tended to centre on individual endeavour rather than exploring the opportunities that slow and collaborative scholarship might bring. Similarly, research that has examined scientific collaboration has often focused on group performance, challenges, and results (e.g., Levine and Moreland, 2004; Sonnenwald, 2007) rather than knowledge creation activities. In this provocation, we draw upon our experiences as an informal network of researchers to argue that virtual collaboration opportunities afforded by the COVID-19 pandemic challenged the method of LIS theoretical development, including the tacit and often taken for granted processes, as well as the final conceptual product.

We are six researchers from Canada, Denmark, Finland, Israel, and the United Kingdom who have spent the last year thinking about transitions from an informational perspective. We started this research collaboration to connect with colleagues in a low-pressure learning experience. Rather than approaching our collaboration with the goal of characterising “transition” as a concept (e.g., Fleming-May, 2011; 2014; Furner, 2004), we engaged in a more open, organic, collaborative process to see what new ideas our different backgrounds and perspectives could spark. Working without an end product in mind meant that we did not see concepts as problems to be resolved but instead as something to be discussed and pondered together. Together, we reviewed scholarly literature on transitions and on information practices and embarked on “discussions, reflections and insights on a series of spirited conversations and debates stemming from a selective review and close reading of earlier literature” (Dalmer & Huvila, 2020, p.97). This slow and collaborative approach to knowledge creation was facilitated by online collaboration opportunities associated with the COVID-19 pandemic, which encouraged our theory development process to become more creative and playful.

Figure 1: Our collaborative process

Together, we followed a meandering path that led us into dead ends and down rabbit holes but allowed us to encounter scholarship we would not otherwise have read and to make surprising connections we wouldn't otherwise have made. The result wasn't what we expected; rather than arriving at a place of convergence, consensus, and conceptualization, we found ourselves in a place of divergence, depth, and deconceptualisation: questioning concepts we had thought we understood. Rather than clear answers, we have come away with deeper relationships and richer questions. Our provocation will discuss our collaborative process and present our reflections on the limitations of dominant individualistic modes of theorising and the possibilities and advantages that slow, collaborative virtual scholarship can bring to LIS.

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